

Synthesis and biological activity of *N*-phenyl-3-methyl-4-(benzothiazol-2'-carboxamido)-5-aryl-2-pyrazolines

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Manuscript received 9 January 2001, revised 7 June 2001, accepted 24 June 2001

2-Acetoacetamidobenzothiazoles (2), prepared by reacting substituted-2-aminobenzothiazoles and methylacetoacetate, are converted into benzothiazol-2-carboxamido- α,β -unsaturated ketones (4) by condensation with different aromatic aldehydes (3). The ketones (4) on refluxing with phenylhydrazine produce the title compounds (5).

Benzothiazoles represent very important class of heterocyclic compounds possessing diversified biological properties¹. Amides containing heterocyclic moiety possess local anaesthetic property². Again pyrazoline derivatives are claimed to have a wide spectrum of biological activities³. Considering all the above facts, it was thought that if benzothiazolcarboxamido group could be introduced to pyrazoline moiety, the resulting compounds might have some significant biological properties.

For this purpose, substituted-2-aminobenzothiazole (1) was treated with methyl acetoacetate to yield 2-acetoacetamidobenzothiazole (2). Compound 2 was then converted into 4 by fusing with different aromatic aldehydes (3). The unsaturated ketone 3-(benzothiazol-2'-carboxamido)-4-arylbut-3-en-2-one (4) was then separately condensed with phenylhydrazine in ethanol using piperidine as condensing agent to form 5 (Scheme 1).

Compounds 5 responded to the Knorr's colour test⁴, a characteristic test for arylpyrazoline. The structures were further confirmed by spectral data⁵.

Experimental

All melting points are uncorrected. The purity of compounds was checked by TLC on silica gel. IR spectra (KBr) were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 781 spectrophotometer.

Substituted 2-aminobenzothiazoles (1) were prepared by using methods reported earlier⁶.

2-Acetoacetamido-6-chloro/methylbenzothiazole (2) : A mixture of 2-amino-6-chloro/methylbenzothiazole (0.01 mol) and methylacetoacetate (0.02 mol) was heated at 160° for 3 h. After cooling, it was poured in water to remove unreacted 2-aminobenzothiazole. The resulting solid was dried, filtered and crystallized from aqueous ethanol as colourless crystals (85%).

Scheme 1

3-(6-Chloro/methylbenzothiazol-2'-carboxamido)-4-arylbut-3-en-2-one (4a-f) : A mixture of 2 (0.01 mol) and the aromatic aldehyde (3; 0.01 mol) was fused on an oil-bath at 100–140° for 1–2 h and then cooled, washed with petroleum ether. The resulting solids were crystallized from suitable solvents (yields 55–70%) : 4a, m.p. 160°, ν_{\max} 1600 (C=N), 1635 (C=O), 750 cm⁻¹ (C-Cl); b, 165°; ν_{\max} 1595 (C=N), 1625 cm⁻¹ (C=O); c, 130°, ν_{\max} 1590 (C=N), 1635 (C=O), 1265 (C-O-C), 750 cm⁻¹ (C-Cl); d, 190°, ν_{\max} 1595 (C=N), 1630 (C=O), 1030 cm⁻¹ (C-O-C); e, 145°, ν_{\max} 1600 (C=N), 1635 (C=O), 1035 (C-O-C), 700 cm⁻¹ (C-Cl); f, 180° 1595 (C=N), 1625 (C=O), 1265 cm⁻¹ (C-O-C).

N-Phenyl-3-methyl-4-(6-chloro/methylbenzothiazol-2'-carboxamido)-5-aryl-2-pyrazoline (**5a-f**): A mixture of **4a-f** (0.05 mol), phenylhydrazine (0.005 mol), ethanol (40 ml) and piperidine (1 ml) was refluxed for 10–12 h. It was then concentrated, cooled and poured in acidified ice-cold water (5% HCl). The resulting solids were crystallized from proper solvent : **5a**, m.p. 170°, ν_{\max} 1627 (C=N), 1710 (C=O), 725 cm^{-1} (C-Cl); **b**, 190°, ν_{\max} 1580 (C=N), 1630 cm^{-1} (C=O); **c**, 150°, ν_{\max} 1615 (C=N), 1625 (C=O), 1030 (C-O-C), 730 cm^{-1} (C-Cl); **d**, 210°, ν_{\max} 1595 (C=N), 1630 (C=O), 1025 cm^{-1} (C-O-C); **e**, 160°, ν_{\max} 1600 (C=N), 1710 (C=O), 1025 (C-O-C), 725 cm^{-1} (C-Cl); **f**, 200°, ν_{\max} 1580 (C=N), 1700 (C=O), 1265 cm^{-1} (C-O-C);

All compounds gave satisfactory C, H, N and S analyses.

Antimicrobial screening : Compounds **2a,b**, **4a-f** and **5a-f** were screened for antimicrobial activity by employing filter paper-disc technique⁷ and tested against *Staphylococci aureus*, *Escherichia coli*, *Pseudomonas*, *Klebsiella* and *Proteus mirabilis*. Compounds **4c,f**, **5f** showed no activity at all. Compounds **4a,b,d** and **5a,b,d** were active against *P. mirabilis* and *Klebsiella*, whereas **4e** and **5e** showed activity against *S. aureus* only and **2a,b** and **5c** showed activity against *P. mirabilis*, *S. aureus* and *Pseudomonas*.

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